

IDENTIFICATION OF δ -VPE ENCODED BY GENOME OF *Theobroma cacao* AND EXPRESSION PATTERN ANALYSIS

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Introduction: The legumains are cysteine proteases belonging to the C13 family (EC 3.4.22.34) found in various types of plants. These proteins are called vacuolar processing enzyme (VPE) or asparaginyl endopeptidase (AEP), by recognize and cleave after asparagine residues (Asn). The VPEs are classified into three groups: vegetative (γ and α VPE), seed (β VPE) and embryogenesis (δ VPE) according to the tissues that are more expressed. The δ -VPE is the least characterized group in literature. **Objective:** Characterized *in silico* the δ -VPE of *Theobroma cacao* and observe its expression pattern in different tissues. **Methodology:** The primary sequences were obtained from the data bank – CocoaGen and subjected to different analyzes *in silico*. The pattern of gene expression was analyzed by quantitative RT-qPCR in different tissues (leaf, stem, root, tegument, cotyledon during germination, seeds in developing and tissue infected with pernicious fungus *Moniliophthora perniciosa*). The expression data were analyzed by Method $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ and normalized with Ct value of the endogenous control established by the software NormFinder. **Results:** A δ -VPE gene was found on loci *Tc06_g006030* (1452pb, 483aa e 53.9 kDa) on genomic library of cocoa, so named: *TcLEG6*. The catalytic residues (His and Cys) remained preserved on performing alignment between *TcLEG6* and a δ -VPE *Arabidopsis thaliana*. In the dendrogram *TcLEG6* protein was inserted into the type from embryogenesis group (δ -VPE). In tissues analyzed, the *TcLeg6* gene was only expressed in developing seeds, where there was an increase of the transcript in the first stage to the third seed stage of development (1.00 para 8.90-X), occurring after a slight decrease of expression (8.90 para 8.70-X). **Conclusion:** *TcLEG6* is inserted into the group of δ -VPEs and may be involved with the removal of the inner layers necessary for the formation of tegument.

Keywords: gene expression, *Theobroma cacao*, δ -VPE.